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DIDACTIC ADVANTAGES OF USING INFORMATION ON INTERNET RESOURCES IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract

The article discusses the use of Internet resources in the learning process. They provide basic information about the use of the Internet, define this textbook, consider its advantages and confirm the relevance of their use in teaching foreign languages. The article is intended for those who are interested in public reading and creating a favorable environment for learning.

Keywords: information technologies 1, Internet resources 2, didactic tasks 3, learning process 4, the Internet 5, high-quality language education 6.

Nowadays, the Internet has become an integral part of the life of a modern person. Mail, telephony and business are moving to the Internet. There are more and more sources of information on the web. The number of network users and the number of information pages is constantly growing. For most young people, the Internet is becoming a familiar and convenient means of communication and information. Students actively use the Internet. 9 out of 10 students use e-mail every day, search the Internet for news, information, work. The Internet is primarily an information network. The presence of a huge amount of materials on the Web and specialized search engines makes the Internet an indispensable tool for finding information in the learning process, both for the teacher and the student.

And we can say that now there is no doubt about the relevance of integrating the Internet into the learning process. At the same time, the main subject of discussion is not the question of why, but how to apply modern computer technologies in the learning process. The use of the Internet would significantly expand the range of real communicative situations, increase the motivation of students, and would allow them to apply the acquired knowledge, skills, and speech skills to solve real communicative problems.

The need to use Internet resources in the educational process in the modern world is due to the following factors:

- fast and cheap access to the necessary information;
- the ability to communicate (Skype, e-mail) with groupmates on educational issues, as well as the ability to contact the teacher;
- access to research and statistical information in preparation for classes (facilitating the implementation of tasks);
- the ability to access encyclopedic information at any time (including photo and video information);
- accessible news search (including economic, legal news, historical reports, speeches of public figures, biographies);
- online distance learning.[1]

If for students the main advantage of using the global network is a convenient, affordable and easy way to find the necessary information, then for teachers the following main advantages of using Internet resources can be distinguished:

- quick search for educational materials for classes;
- the ability to quickly access the regulatory framework;

- searching and receiving information about ongoing conferences, programs, competitions, sending applications, abstracts, articles, reports and speeches at conferences, publishing their work;

- advanced training based on materials and information available on the global network, etc.;

The main advantages of using the Internet in the educational process for students include:

- improving computer literacy (improving the skills of handling and working with a computer and the Internet);

- developing and improving the skills of independent search for the necessary information and work with it, as well as training and research;

- formation of practical skills.[2]

A striking example of the use of the global Internet in the educational process is distance learning. This relatively new form of education is an alternative to the most common traditional education at present.

Distance learning has become possible due to the rapid development of Internet technologies, the widespread use of computers not only in the work of organizations, but also at home and their popularization. A distinctive feature of distance learning is the ability of students to independently seek and obtain the necessary knowledge with the help of information resources. It should be noted that the information resources of the global network in the learning process are used not only by students of this form of education, but also by all other forms, because searching for information on the Internet is available to almost everyone and saves a lot of time.

Internet information resources used in the learning process include:

- databases, information systems, reference files, dictionaries, reference books;

- training systems, courses, programs for self-education;

- educational video and audio recordings;

- electronic libraries (newspapers, magazines, books in electronic form);

- distance learning courses;

- email, etc.[3]

N.V. Ivanova highlights the following advantages of using Internet resources:

- Internet resources guarantee the transfer of knowledge and access to information much faster and more efficiently than traditional learning tools. Textbooks and manuals in foreign languages have been republished for a long time, because of this, the information in them ceases to be relevant for students;

- Internet resources should be considered as a new pedagogical technology, since the position of the teacher changes, he ceases to be the only source of knowledge, but becomes the initiator of the process of searching, processing information and coordinating the research and creation of students' creative works;

- The Internet forms the general educational skills of students related to analysis, synthesis, abstraction, comparison, collation, generalization, as well as the mechanisms of probabilistic-semantic forecasting, language attentiveness and language observation;

- When teaching language to students, online resources can help the teacher build productive and speaking skills, ensuring that students are truly engaged in learning outcomes. The goal of the teacher is to teach pupils and students to respond spontaneously and adequately to the statements of native speakers or classmates, showing their own emotions and feelings, rebuilding right on the go, thus, the implementation of the activity approach in learning takes place. foreign language;

- The Internet contributes to the formation of such socio-psychological qualities of students as self-confidence and the ability to work individually and in a team; creates an excellent atmosphere for cooperation, being a means of an interactive approach. Interactivity encourages students to adequately respond to real life situations with the help of a foreign language.

- Internet resources are an invaluable and immense tool that creates an information-subject environment for learning and self-education of students that meets their individual interests and needs. Possessing such a distinctive feature as a high degree of interactivity, information content.[4]

Internet resources create a unique educational and cognitive environment that can be productively used to solve didactic tasks in teaching a foreign language:

- development of skills and formation of reading skills based on the use of authentic materials of varying complexity, taking into account the characteristics of the learning stage;

- improving the ability to perceive foreign speech by ear, using authentic Internet audio texts and a series of communicative exercises to control the understanding of what is heard;

- improving writing skills individually or collectively (writing a response letter to partners, selecting abstract material, writing essays with elements of reasoning, performing creative projects);

- replenishment of the vocabulary with a dictionary of modern English, reflecting a certain period in the development of the culture of the people, the socio-political and economic structure of society;

- acquaintance with cultural knowledge, characterized by speech etiquette, characteristic features of verbal and non-verbal behavior of native speakers, cultural characteristics, traditions of the country of the language being studied;

- the formation of a sustainable motivation for foreign language activities in the classroom based on the regular use of relevant materials, the discussion of issues of interest to all.[5]

The main advantage of computer telecommunications is the isolation of the electronic information environment, which allows students and teachers to work with computers as universal means of information processing.

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that information technology allows:

- organize joint diverse research work and projects of students, teachers, students of different schools, educational and scientific centers from different regions and countries;

- provide operational consulting support to a wide range of students of scientific and methodological centers;
- to organize distance learning and advanced training of the teaching staff;
- promptly exchange information, data, ideas, thoughts, plans that are of interest to participants, expand their horizons and raise their cultural level;
- instill the skills of real research activities, imitating the work of a scientific laboratory, a creative workshop;
- develop the ability to find information in various sources, process it with the support of modern computer technologies, store and transmit it over long distances, to different parts of the world;
- reproduce the real language environment (subject to the compatibility of international telecommunications projects, audio, television, video conferences, chats), which will contribute to the emergence of a natural need for communication
- in a foreign language, and, consequently, the need to study foreign languages;
- to promote the cultural, humanitarian development of students based on access to extensive information of a cultural, ethnic, humanistic nature.[6]

It is these advantages of the Internet that become apparent when it is used in the classroom. For such work, the ideal condition is the presence of a computer class with Internet access.

The use of Internet resources is not an end in itself. In order to correctly determine the place, significance

and role of the Internet in the pedagogical process, it is necessary, firstly, to find answers to the questions: for whom, for what, when and to what extent it should be used.

The introduction of Internet resources is not only a compliance with educational trends, but also an innovation that a modern teacher should have.[7]

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